

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

PROJECT ACRONYM: RECAP

PROJECT NUMBER: 693171

PROJECT FULL TITLE: Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the CAP

WORK PACKAGE NUMBER & NAME:

WP.5 Dissemination & Exploitation

DELIVERABLE NUMBER & NAME:

D5.9 Project Workshops (2)

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Project Full Title: Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the CAP

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1.0	8/11/2018	Draft	Draft for review	ETAM SA
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3.0	14/11/2018	Final	Final version	ETAM SA

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Deliverable D5.9 “Project Workshops” (2) provides an overview and details on the workshops carried out in pilot countries and their evaluation results.

The concept behind the organization of the workshops was to gather potential stakeholders/users of the platform, in order to exchange information and thoughts on the RECAP platform and its components. At the same time they offered the opportunity to test the RECAP platform. The workshops’ outcomes in turn provided useful feedback on the user satisfaction of the RECAP product, increasing its chances for market uptake.

The workshops were carried out in each of the four pilot countries (Greece, UK, Spain, Lithuania). Their aim was to present the RECAP platform as it was to be tested, along with the logistics of the pilots, in order to allow local pilot partners to better involve the pilot actors as well as get the interest from other national stakeholders.

It should be noted that by organizing these events for launching the pilots, dissemination and communication goals were also served. Promotional actions for the workshops, as well as the participants themselves, maximized dissemination of the project. Subsequently, the RECAP product increased in visibility at a local / regional level. The Network of Interest was also enriched by adding workshop members in the core – user group.

The RECAP final event was organized as a satellite to a larger event. The final meeting event was organized in the frames of INSPIRE conference that was held from 18 to 21 September, by the European Commission, in Antwerp, Belgium. A presentation of RECAP took place at the parallel sessions held in the thematic GEOINT for Environmental Compliance Assurance in rural areas/agriculture where at least 40 individuals attended the presentation expanding further the NoI. The project consortium had the opportunity to share experiences and present project results to a broad audience of officers and professional stakeholders. Amongst others, several representatives of EU and national public institutions as well as farmers’ representatives and experts from the EO industry attended and actively participated in the open discussion of the workshop.

2. INTRODUCTION

The deliverable 5.9 “Project Workshops (2)” analyses details on the workshops carried out and their evaluation results.

The methodology decided upon preparing the workshops was the object of the previous version of the deliverable 5.5 (M14) with relative instructions for carrying out a successful workshop, in line with its aims. It included, templates of various forms useful for organizational or dissemination purposes. The targeted metrics of the RECAP project was to successfully carry out four regional workshops, one in each pilot country (Greece, UK, Lithuania and Serbia).

Tools available for all pilot partners as designed in the first deliverable were

- a) *The workshop agenda*
- b) *Attendees questionnaire on their satisfaction and /or suggestions on the RECAP product*
- c) *Workshop Inventory*
- d) *Registration list*
- e) *Invitation letter*

This deliverable analytically presents all organization and dissemination actions that took place for launching the pilot workshops, actions at the preparation stage, the day of the event and relative retrospective actions. The deliverable also presents an evaluation of the workshops results and also includes details on the dissemination actions, survey results, attendances etc.

3. THE WORKSHOPS IN GREECE

3.1 Workshops

The Greek pilot workshops took place in Larisa Thessaly at the Local Branch of the Geotechnical Chamber of Greece. Larissa was selected as a Nitrate Vulnerable Zone and the main agricultural production zone of Greece, whilst the venue of choice that hosted the events is a reference point for local farmers and agricultural consultants.

The first workshop was held on the 11th of December 2017 and it was addressing mainly agricultural consultants and representatives from Basic Payment Schemes Application Centres. The second workshop was held on the 29th of January 2018 addressing farmers. These two workshops managed to involve 75 Agricultural Consultants of Greece and representatives from Basic Payment Schemes Application Centres and 45 Farmers.

The local workshops' organising team was:

- ☑ Lead Workshop Organizer: Kostas Kountouris
- ☑ Workshop IT Expert: Nikos Petalidis
- ☑ Project Assistants / Event Coordinators: Argiro Kranidioti
- ☑ Workshop Instructors / Facilitators Moderators: Olga Tzouvara, Maria Iordanidou

Guest speakers invited were Giannis Kargiotis (GENERAL DIRECTOR OF OPEKEPE) and Sakis Valiotis (LOCAL DIRECTOR) who both are highly recognizable and accountable for their expertise in Greece.

Real time posts on RECAP social media

3.2 Dissemination actions

Prior to the workshops an invitation letter was sent to local newspapers, announcements were made in local associations and cooperations and GEOTEE mass mailed the workshop invitation to its local members. The events were also disseminated through RECAP & OPEKEPE website and posts were made on social media real time. The events received significant publicity and were promoted by a number of local and national media.

Social media posts

RECAP H2020 Project
7 Δεκεμβρίου 2017

Project event hosted by the Payment and Control Agency for Guidance and Guarantee Community Aid of Greece, Larissa on Monday 11/12/2017.
Read more at: <https://www.recap-h2020.eu/project-event-in-larissa/>
#RECAP #remote_sensing #agricultural_sector #environment #CAP

Δείτε τη μετάφραση

RECAP-H2020.EU
Project event in Larissa - Recap - Reinforcing CAP - Personalized Public Services in Support of the...

Ο χρήστης RECAP H2020 Project κοινοποίησε μια δημοσίευση.
29 Ιανουαρίου

Σε περίπου μία ώρα θα ξεκινήσει η εκδήλωση ενημέρωσης που διοργανώνει ο ΟΠΕΚΕΠΕ στη Λάρισα !!!

PERSONALISED PUBLIC SERVICES IN SUPPORT OF THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CAP

RECAP
Reinforcing CAP

Π Ρ Ο Σ Κ Λ Η Σ Η

Ο Ο.Π.Ε.Κ.Ε.Π.Ε. προσκαλεί τους **Αγρότες - Παραγωγούς** της περιοχής Θεσσαλίας στη 2^η Ενημερωτική – Εκπαιδευτική Εκδήλωση για το ευρωπαϊκό ερευνητικό πρόγραμμα «Personalised public services in support of the implementation of the new CAP (RECAP)» το οποίο αφορά στη βελτίωση της αποτελεσματικότητας εφαρμογής της Πολυαπλής Συμμόρφωσης και του Πρασίνισματος από τους αγροτικούς συντελεστές (αγρότες, γεωργικούς συμβούλους κλπ) μέσω αυτοματοποιημένων μεθόδων τηλεπικοινωνίας και πληροφορικής. Στην εκδήλωση θα παρουσιαστεί η νέα πλατφόρμα και θα επιδειχθεί προώγηση των μέγιστου δυνατού αριθμού πιλοτικών χρηστών για τον έλεγχο της λειτουργικότητας και της αποτελεσματικότητας της πλατφόρμας.

29 Ιανουαρίου 2018
Πρα 11:00-13:30μ.μ.

Παράρτημα Κεντρικής Ελλάδας ΓΕΩ.Τ.Ε.Ε.
Καψούρη 4, 41222 Λάρισα

Το έργο έχει λάβει χρηματοδότηση από το πρόγραμμα της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης για την ανάπτυξη της οικονομίας Έκτακτη 2020 στο πλαίσιο του συγκεκριμένου αναγκασίας, αριθμ. 480171.

RECAP H2020 Project
22 Ιανουαρίου

Ο ΟΠΕΚΕΠΕ, μέλος του εταιρικού σχήματος του ερευνητικού έργου RECAP H2020, διοργανώνει την προσεχή Δευτέρα 29/1/2018 στη Λάρισα, εκδήλωση ενημέρωσης αγροτών και παραγωγών, σχετικά με την ηλεκτρονική πλατφόρμα του RECAP.
Read more: <https://www.recap-h2020.eu/2nd-project-event-in-larissa/>
#RECAP #remote_sensing #agricultural_sector #environment #CAP

3.3 Feedback from participants

Workshops organized provided valuable feedback for the implementation of RECAP. Feedback from the **workshop in Larisa** provided valuable information and specifically the main outcomes were that it is:

- Very useful for consultants.
- Rather difficult for farmers (due to the low familiarization with IT in general).
- A great facilitation for electronic record keeping.
- The work diary functionality of the platform is extremely useful for Nitrogen balance calculation.
- Useful for Information / Notifications for audits.
- Useful for non eligible areas.

4. THE WORKSHOPS IN SERBIA

4.1 Workshops

In Serbia, workshops started as early as September 2017 and lasted until the launching of the pilot implementation. The strategy behind the workshops early start was to present the RECAP project (and platform) and to organise the first round of trainings for Organic Farmers during the regional Organic Production events in order to reach more future participants.

Three (3) workshops were organised in a large scale addressing farmers whilst a series of work meetings were organised addressing the Serbian Authorities and Certification Bodies.

The local RECAP team was responsible for the organisation of workshops.

The specific roles assigned to team members were:

1. Maja Budimir – leader, RECAP platform presenter and training instructor
2. Vladimir Mrkajić – facilitator, training instructor
3. Nemanja Nićin – support and assistance in overall coordination
4. Maja Žigić – support and assistance in external communication
5. Ivana Botić - support and assistance in overall coordination

Technical Assistance was assigned to a representative of the RECAP platform development team, Aleksandar Sekulić - ICT specialist.

The first two workshops were part of Organic Production events. Specifically the first workshop was organised in the frames of the “Forum for Organic Producers” held in Selenča village on the 29th of September 2017. The second workshop was organised in the frames of Terras.org - Biofest: IT Organic Vision of Future in Subotica on the 12th of October 2017.

The main focus of these events was current agri-tech solutions in Serbia and how these tools can be useful for Organic Farming. In this way, RECAP received great publicity and the platform was positively commented on and supported by respective experts from the field of ICT, organic production and public service representatives that were present in the events.

1st workshops invitation	Workshop agenda																				
<p>11. FORUM O ORGANSKOJ PROIZVODNJI Selenča 29. septembar 2017. godine</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Vreme</th> <th>Program</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>10:00 – 10:30</td> <td>Registracija učesnika</td> </tr> <tr> <td>10:30 – 11:15</td> <td>Konferencija za medije - prezentacija projekta ORGANIC BRIDGE (Program Interreg IPA CBC Croatia–Serbia) - Jozef Galperović, stručnjak Centra za organsku proizvodnju Selenča - Vuk Radujević, Pokrajinski sekretar za poljoprivredu, vodoprivredu i šumarstvo - dr. sc. Stjepan Glas, opunomoćeni ministar Ambasade Republike Hrvatske u Republici Srbiji - Lidija Maurović Kokić, direktorica Lokalne razvojne agencije grada Valpova (Hrvatska)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>11:15 – 11:30</td> <td>Pausa za kafu</td> </tr> <tr> <td>11:30 – 11:40</td> <td>Pozdravni govori - Dragomir Stalević, predsednik Opštine Rač - Velimir Stanojević, državni sekretar u Ministarstvu poljoprivrede, vodoprivrede i šumarstva - Nj.E. Dragomir Repčićević, ambasadorica Slovačke Republike u Republici Srbiji</td> </tr> <tr> <td>11:40 – 11:45</td> <td>Otvoravanje glavnog dela Foruma - Julijana Schusterova, tehnički ekspert Slovačke za organsku proizvodnju pri Evropskoj uniji Dodela medijskih nagrada SELENA ORGANIK 2017 - Đuro Božić, direktor Slovan progress i osnivač Centra za organsku proizvodnju Selenča</td> </tr> <tr> <td>11:45 – 13:00</td> <td>Panel diskusija: Izazovi i perspektive - kuda ide Srbija (Moderator: Goran Živković) - Velimir Stanojević, državni sekretar u Ministarstvu poljoprivrede, vodoprivrede i šumarstva - Miruzka Božić, ekspert za poljoprivredu i ruralni razvoj (Hrvatska) - Sata Vindovič, direktor PS Global seed i osnivač Centra za organsku proizvodnju Selenča - Vuk Radujević, Pokrajinski sekretar za poljoprivredu, vodoprivredu i šumarstvo</td> </tr> <tr> <td>13:00 – 14:00</td> <td>Ručak i Međunarodni festival tradicionalne proizvedene hrane</td> </tr> <tr> <td>14:00 – 15:00</td> <td>Prezentacija ReCAP projekta - Modernizacija organske poljoprivrede - proizvodnja, pa papirologija</td> </tr> <tr> <td>14:00 – 17:00</td> <td>Međunarodni poslovni sastavi B2B2017: u skladu sa rasporedom kreiranim na bazi prijave učesnika</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Vreme	Program	10:00 – 10:30	Registracija učesnika	10:30 – 11:15	Konferencija za medije - prezentacija projekta ORGANIC BRIDGE (Program Interreg IPA CBC Croatia–Serbia) - Jozef Galperović, stručnjak Centra za organsku proizvodnju Selenča - Vuk Radujević, Pokrajinski sekretar za poljoprivredu, vodoprivredu i šumarstvo - dr. sc. Stjepan Glas, opunomoćeni ministar Ambasade Republike Hrvatske u Republici Srbiji - Lidija Maurović Kokić, direktorica Lokalne razvojne agencije grada Valpova (Hrvatska)	11:15 – 11:30	Pausa za kafu	11:30 – 11:40	Pozdravni govori - Dragomir Stalević, predsednik Opštine Rač - Velimir Stanojević, državni sekretar u Ministarstvu poljoprivrede, vodoprivrede i šumarstva - Nj.E. Dragomir Repčićević, ambasadorica Slovačke Republike u Republici Srbiji	11:40 – 11:45	Otvoravanje glavnog dela Foruma - Julijana Schusterova, tehnički ekspert Slovačke za organsku proizvodnju pri Evropskoj uniji Dodela medijskih nagrada SELENA ORGANIK 2017 - Đuro Božić, direktor Slovan progress i osnivač Centra za organsku proizvodnju Selenča	11:45 – 13:00	Panel diskusija: Izazovi i perspektive - kuda ide Srbija (Moderator: Goran Živković) - Velimir Stanojević, državni sekretar u Ministarstvu poljoprivrede, vodoprivrede i šumarstva - Miruzka Božić, ekspert za poljoprivredu i ruralni razvoj (Hrvatska) - Sata Vindovič, direktor PS Global seed i osnivač Centra za organsku proizvodnju Selenča - Vuk Radujević, Pokrajinski sekretar za poljoprivredu, vodoprivredu i šumarstvo	13:00 – 14:00	Ručak i Međunarodni festival tradicionalne proizvedene hrane	14:00 – 15:00	Prezentacija ReCAP projekta - Modernizacija organske poljoprivrede - proizvodnja, pa papirologija	14:00 – 17:00	Međunarodni poslovni sastavi B2B2017: u skladu sa rasporedom kreiranim na bazi prijave učesnika	
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Workshop in Subotica	Dissemination materials

The 3rd workshop was organised by InoSens in Novi Sad at the EU Info Point on the 6th of November 2017.

Participation in these workshops is hard to estimate as the first two workshops were part of larger scale events. Attendance sheets therefore were not practical to be distributed and were only partly completed. It is roughly estimated that around 150 farmers attended these workshops.

Digitalna organska poljoprivreda
KAKO SMANJITI NEPOTREBNU DOKUMENTACIJU?
EU INFO POINT NOVI SAD
Bulevar Mihajla Pupina 17
06. novembar | 13-14:30h

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No83121.

Samples of attendance sheets

Ime i prezime	Naziv gostinstva/kompanije	Mesto	Email	Telefon
LEVA BROJANAC Svojim-a TOLIC	PROJEKTOVANJE POSREDOVANJE POSREDOVANJE POSREDOVANJE	Novi Sad	PROJEKTOVANJE POSREDOVANJE POSREDOVANJE	060 613334
RANKO GANTNER	POLJOPRIVRAG POSREDOVANJE	OSINEC	POSREDOVANJE	069 725577
GORAN RODIC	POSREDOVANJE	KUPINIK	POSREDOVANJE	069 725577
MILICA COSTI	POSREDOVANJE	TEMERIN	POSREDOVANJE	069 725577
Radoslav Jovanovic	JR. Tempo food	Trstenik	POSREDOVANJE	069 725577

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 Proizvodi
 2. Vrh -
 nije se
 pojavio
 u listi
 OCS - Miroslav Novakovic

Ime i prezime	Naziv gostinstva/kompanije	Mesto	Email	Telefon
FRANKO PANDIC	POSREDOVANJE	ZAMARATA	POSREDOVANJE	060 613334
DORIS DIZIC	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	069 725577
MARINA DOLJAC	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	069 725577
IVANA KEPAC	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	069 725577
POSREDOVANJE POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	069 725577
POSREDOVANJE POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	069 725577
POSREDOVANJE POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	POSREDOVANJE	069 725577
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 2
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 u listi
 OCS - Miroslav Novakovic

Workshops were also organised for the benefit of the Serbian Paying Agency and Certification Bodies. The strategy behind these workshops was to avoid large scale events and focus on individual meetings in order to achieve better results.

Five meetings - workshops were organised for Certification Bodies Staff and namely TMS, ETKOPANONIA, OCS, ECOCERT and CIN. Two additional meetings took place for individual Certification Body Consultants. In total 18 representatives of Certification Bodies were reached through these workshops and they were carried out from the 13th of November 2018 until the 22nd of January 2018.

Finally, a one-to-one meeting was organised in the premises of Serbian PA on 23rd of February 2018 in Belgrade. During this meeting, the Local Team presented the RECAP project and platform for three (3) PA representatives.

4.2 Dissemination actions

Dissemination actions of the workshops initially focused on person – to – person communications with representatives of the Paying Agency and Certification Bodies, so as to manage successful and focused communication of the project with their contribution.

Pre-workshop dissemination was well planned ahead. Invitations were sent out to selected participants and were also made public both by media posts on regional agro-portals and contacts lists of Organic Cooperatives. Press releases after the events were also published, announcing at the same time the invitation for next the workshop.

Links of all media coverages during “workshops phase”:

- ☑ <http://terras.org.rs/13-medjunarodni-festival-organskih-proizvoda/>
- ☑ <http://www.ecofeminizam.com/2017/10/17/projekat-recap/>
- ☑ <http://www.agronews.rs/platforma-recap-digitalna-pomoc-organskim-proizvodacima/>
<https://www.kvalitet.org.rs/ostalo/6039-srbija-na-korak-do-digitalne-organske-poljoprivrede>
- ☑ <http://euinfo.rs/recap-platforma-za-efikasniju-brzu-i-moderniju-organsku-proizvodnju-i-prodaju/>
- ☑ <https://www.subotica.info/2017/10/14/13-medunarodni-festival-organskih-proizvoda-biofest-2017>
- ☑ <http://www.serbiaorganica.info/pocela-sa-radom-nova-platformaaplikacija-namenjena-organskim-proizvodacima/>
- ☑ <http://www.agrosmart.net/organska-poljoprivreda/organski-proizvodaci-srbiji-bice-spremni.html>

Additionally during the 1st and initial workshop, on the Forum for Organic Producers, in Selenča on 29.09.2017 – the presentation was disseminated in social media real time, on the FB profile of InoSens.

Introducing Serbian organic farmers / RECAP H2020 Project platform – the link:

<https://www.facebook.com/inosensrs/videos/536036683395341/>

4.3 Feedback from participants

Serbia’s workshops have provided important feedback especially given that workshops organized have reached out different core groups comparing to other pilot countries. The following results were collected per group type:

Organic Farmers:

- ✔ The platform is a useful tool for simplifying the overall document management of organic subsidy scheme and certification process.
- ✔ Difficult for farmers that are not very familiar with IT in general.
- ✔ Organic Farmers that possess a farm registered as a Legal entity in Serbia, noticed that RECAP platform workflow was missing some information that is necessary for completion of their application process for organic subsidies. With the help of the RECAP development team, extra blank spaces for such information were added.
- ✔ Automatic creation of parcels by entering the cadastral number, was suggested as very useful (farmers with more improved IT skills) - could be added on the platform.

Payment Agency (Directorate for Agrarian Payments):

- ✔ Greater control over subsidy scheme and each Organic Farmer.
- ✔ Remote Sensing component is a very useful feature that could be exploited more.
- ✔ More simplified documentation process.
- ✔ As a support for implementation of the CAP, they see the platform as a useful tool for future CAP implementation in Serbia.

Certification Bodies:

- ✔ Useful for the control during certification process – monitoring of certified quantities of organic crops.
- ✔ More simplified documentation process.
- ✔ Possibility for the record keeping – positive comment.
- ✔ Possibility to automatically create parcel by entering cadastral parcel number is perceived to be very useful – should be added on the platform.
- ✔ Prevention of fraud (double) registration of one parcel in two or more certification bodies – RECAP could help.

5. THE WORKSHOPS IN THE UK

5.1 Workshops

In the UK, two workshops were organised. The first event was held at Rothamsted Research Institute Harpenden, an Agricultural research centre, on the 20th of February 2018. The workshop was addressing farmers and the strategy behind the choice of venue was its central location within the Remote Sensing area. Edward Hutley of Strutt & Parker presented the RECAP platform with screenshots and highlighted how it could be useful to Farmers to meet Cross Compliance requirements. Fifty two (52) stakeholders attended (16 consultants, 34 farmers, 2 researchers) the workshop and twenty (20) out of thirty four (34) farmers signed up to the Pilot.

The second workshop was held on the 21st of March 2018 at the London Club for Farmers, a central location for agricultural consultants. A presentation was given to explain the RECAP platform to the national consultancy team and twenty three (23) agricultural consultants attended.

The Local RECAP team was responsible for the organisation of workshops. The specific roles assigned to team members were:

1. Edward Hutley, workshop leader
2. George Badger ,IT expert
3. Jason Beedell, assistant
4. Alice Mauchline assistant
5. Kate Johnson, assistant

Jonathan Storkey (Rothamsted Researcher) and Kate Johnson (UREAD) were invited in the workshop team as Guest speakers.

1st workshop	2nd workshop

5.2 Dissemination actions

Pre-workshop dissemination actions organized involved personal communications with interested parties and mailing Invitation letters to S&P mailing list. The event was also disseminated in social media real time.

5.3 Feedback from participants

The workshops were successful in their implementation as the majority of farmers that attended them signed up to the Pilot.

The **workshop** having addressed farmers and agricultural consultants reached the following findings:

- Increased visibility and communication with the PA would be welcomed
- Platform looks easy to navigate
- Entering data for large farms may be time consuming
- Would like to see a mobile version for ease of uploading documents
- Consultants are expected to use the platform on behalf of Farmers

6. THE WORKSHOPS IN SPAIN

6.1 Workshops

Two workshops were organized to facilitate access to farmers on two different dates August 30, and September 6, 2018 in the facilities of INTIA.

Each of the two workshops was organized with the participation of all the technical team involved in the RECAP project:

- ✔ An instructor specialized in cross compliance issues (José Angel Garraza).
- ✔ A technical consultant specialized in the management of the RECAP platform (Cristina Virto) and
- ✔ A technician responsible for the project (Alberto Lafarga), the presentation of RECAP and its development context and future use expectations.
- ✔ A special role was always played by the technical advisor of the cooperative, Javier Torrecilla, as a person close to the farmers' problems.

Agenda of the workshops:

- ✔ Introduction of the RECAP project. Alberto Lafarga and Javier Torrecilla.
- ✔ Presentation of the cross compliance applied in Navarra. José Angel Garraza and Cristina Virto.
- ✔ Presentation of the Platform's functionalities and practices with the farmers attending their plots. Alberto Lafarga and Javier Torrecilla.
- ✔ Personal realization of the surveys. Cristina Virto.
- ✔ Focus Group, debate on the main points and analysis of the main functionalities within the group framework. Alberto Lafarga.

Five (5) farmers participated in each workshop representing a total of 50 CAP Declarations.

The invitations were made to the most significant farmers and professionals who represent several CAP declarants, with which the impact of the workshops would be more important.

Currently in Spain, many of the traditional small farmers have disappeared, although they still maintain ownership of the land and are still administratively the CAP Declarants. These Declarants delegate the daily management of the crops to professional farmers through different renting models. For this reason, professional farmers represent the interests of the CAP Declarants and make the most appropriate decisions in all matters of cultivation and CAP commitments and cross compliance.

Attendance sheet	1st Workshop 2018	2nd Workshop 2018

6.2 Dissemination actions

Pre-workshop dissemination actions of the workshops consisted interviews conducted by the technical advisor of the cooperative Orvalaiz, Javier Torrecilla, with the most significant farmers. In these personal interviews the technical advisor presented the RECAP platform to each of the farmers and invited them personally to attend a workshop meeting in which they learned more about the functionalities and services that RECAP could offer to each one of them.

Events were also disseminated in social media real time.

<https://twitter.com/NavarraAgraria/status/1027456663605993472>

<https://twitter.com/NavarraAgraria/status/1027489909647409152>

<https://twitter.com/NavarraAgraria/status/1027147296008560641>

6.3 Feedback from participants

The conclusions as expressed in a relative debate that took place at the end of the two workshops are presented in the following:

1) Platform strengths/advantages:

Cross-compliance norms, self-check and calculator:

Farmers believe it is useful to have a tool allowing identifying each parcel with each cross-compliance norm it has to fulfill. It is however necessary that the platform is fed by the Paying Agency with the specific requirements for each declared parcel (massive upload of info).

They also found it interesting to be able to self-check of what can or cannot do in each parcel and the way they will have to justify it.

They stated that it would be important to involve the inspector in a pre-inspection stage to suggest what the farmer should do to comply with each commitment or requirement, photographs, documents, questionnaire, etc.

Uploading of photos to verify that they are complying with the norm was not considered to be very "reliable". The greening calculator was regarded as interesting and useful by everyone.

Crop identification

Crop identification by remote sensing has been regarded as very useful by farmers. One of the strongest points of the platform is the "traffic light" procedure of classifying as "green", if the crop coincides, yellow if it is doubtful and red if it does not coincide. Farmers regard this point as one of the strengths of the platform for correcting possible errors in the administrative claim.

In this respect, it is regarded as important that the massive upload of crop claims is conducted early on, at the outset of the cropping season.

CAP claim

They suggested the CAP claim could be made through the platform.

Maps

Farmers believe Sentinel images to be of great importance for crop monitoring through. However, they worry about its operability, that is if the images will be available quickly and the indexes will be safely calculated (without cloud interference).

2) Platform weaknesses/disadvantages:

- It is necessary and of utmost importance that a massive upload of parcel claims can be conducted for the interested users.
- Some of the functions of the platform are already made by another platform, so they seem quite repetitive. For example, the visualization of parcels. They think that the most efficient thing would be to have a single platform, and adding the new and interesting functions of RECAP platform to it (e.g. list of cross-compliance norms, self-checking, greening, crop identification).
- The advisor cannot visualize more than one farmer user at the same time. This is a disadvantage as it will be of help that he/she could access different users simultaneously in order to send general messages. The same applies for visualizing parcels. It would also be of interest if the advisor could visualize all parcels of interest at the same time, even from different farmers.
- One of the greatest weaknesses /disadvantages is that each user corresponds to one CAP claim, while there are many farmers that have many CAP claims. The platform does not allow for them to visualize all parcels at the same time, only those corresponding to a single claim. This is regarded as a major hurdle for users and a very necessary modification to implement.
- The app only works with Android. It should also be made available for iPhone.
- The work diary is not sufficiently operative. It is better to use other platforms to this aim, which prepare field notebooks tailored to the region or the user.

7. THE LITHUANIAN WORKSHOP

7.1 Workshop

The first workshop in Lithuania was organized on the 5th of June 2018 (on national scope). The aim of the workshop was to discuss the process of pilot activities. It was planned to organize trainings for advisors in order to introduce them with the project and its aims, as well as to present the platform to advisors first, to explain what documents they would have to fill in and what pilot activities they would have to fulfill together with farmers. In other words, the workshop was organized in order to discuss the organizational issues of training activities of agricultural advisors. In this first workshop six (6) advisors participated.

The second workshop was organized on the 15th, 19th, and 29th June 2018 at LAAS and carried out online. In this three day workshop trainings for 6 groups of advisors took place (total number of participants: 65 agricultural advisors and crop specialists). The aim was to provide information for advisors about pilot activities.

The workshops were held at LAAS headquarters and coordinated by LAAS’s Gintarė Kučinskienė, Kristina Narvidienė and Ligita Titiškytė.

Workshop 1 attendance list	Workshop 2 indicative attendance list																					
<p>The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface for 'RECAP Ireland (7 attend)'. It displays a list of participants on the left and a grid of video thumbnails for the attendees. The participants listed are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indrėna Narvidienė Štepanas Rytkevičius Tomasa Švedienė Ligita Titiškytė Audronė Matulevičiūtė Gintarė Kučinskienė Indrėna Narvidienė Tomasa Švedienė Ligita Titiškytė Audronė Matulevičiūtė Gintarė Kučinskienė Indrėna Narvidienė Tomasa Švedienė Ligita Titiškytė Audronė Matulevičiūtė Gintarė Kučinskienė 																						
No.	Name (Last, First, Surname)	Position																				
1	Audronė Matulevičiūtė (MPh)	Chief Specialist at Control Coordination Unit (MPh)																				
2	Štepanas Rytkevičius	Chief Specialist at Communication Unit (MPh)																				
3	Gintarė Kučinskienė (LAAS)	Head of Department of Innovation Development																				
4	Ligita Titiškytė (LAAS)	Project Management Specialist																				
5	Indrėna Narvidienė (LAAS)	Chief Production Expert																				
6	Tomasa Švedienė (LAAS)	Senior Engineer of Information Technology Systems																				

7.2 Dissemination actions

Dissemination actions focused on person to person communications mainly via e-mails and phone calls.

7.3 Feedback from participants

Lithuania workshops came to the following conclusions:

- The use of similar tools was helpful and useful and they would be willing to use such a tool in the future.

- Comments provided were that improvements are necessary for map site and greening calculator, and the for an app and interrelation of reminders and e-mails/SMS.
- One third of the respondents stated that they would be willing to pay for services in the platform.

8. The final event

8.1 The final event workshop

The final meeting event was organized in the frames of INSPIRE conference that was held from 18 to 21 September, by the European Commission, in Antwerp, Belgium.

INSPIRE stands for Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe and it is a Directive aiming to create a European Union spatial data infrastructure for the purposes of EU environmental policies and policies or activities which may have an impact on the environment. This European Spatial Data Infrastructure enables the sharing of environmental spatial information among public sector organisations, facilitates public access to spatial information across Europe and assists in policy-making across boundaries.

Considering the focus of the conference, the size (last year more than 1000 participants) and the timing (towards the end of RECAP; also having results from the pilot implementation) and the fact that DG CONCT has asked for the participation/presentation of RECAP project, the decision to organize the final event within the INSPIRE conference was taken.

The presentation of RECAP took place at the parallel sessions held in the thematic GEOINT for Environmental Compliance Assurance in rural areas/agriculture where at least 40 individuals attended the presentation expanding further the Nol. The project consortium had the opportunity to share experiences and present project results to a broad audience of stakeholders. Amongst others, several representatives of EU and national public institutions as well as farmers' representatives and experts from the EO industry attended and actively participated in the open discussion of the workshop.

8.2 8.2 Dissemination actions

INSPIRE conference is itself a high visibility event. Therefore the event was disseminated both by the REACP team and the conferences' organizers. It was made public through the INSPIRE & RECAP website, and also their social media accounts.

Ο χρήστης **RECAP H2020 Project** κοινοποίησε μια δημοσίευση. ...
28 Αυγούστου · 🌐

RECAP H2020 PROJECT
THE FINAL EVENT

Can we transform knowledge, Earth Observation & user-generated data into added value services for CAP monitoring?

JOIN US

INSPIRE Conference
Antwerp, 19 September 2018

Draxis
28 Αυγούστου · 🌐 👍 Μου αρέσει η Σελίδα!

RECAP H2020 Project Final Event @Inspire Conference 2018
When: 19th of September
Where: Antwerp, Belgium
We are so happy to announce that RECAP, our H2020 proje...
Δείτε περισσότερα

Δείτε τη μετάφραση

👤 Dimitris Lamas, Ioanna Antonopoulou και 8 ακόμη 1 κοινοποίηση

<https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/conferences/2018/inspire>

15:00	Brownfield Site Registers in England: Delivering with INSPIRE through a standard approach	Jason King 🇬🇧
15:15	Combining Attribute Data and Spatial Datasets with the Updated Table Joining Service Standard	Peika Litvaks 🇬🇧
Enabling a more efficient monitoring of the Common Agricultural Policy using open satellite and user generated data – The RECAP H2020 project - 19/09/2018 - 14:00		
		Chair: Ms. Machi Simeonidou - DRAXIS Environmental
Enabling a more efficient monitoring of the Common Agriculture Policy using open satellite and user generated data – The RECAP H2020 project		Machi Simeonidou 🇬🇧

Posts were also made on RECAP Social media real time:

Ο χρήστης **RECAP H2020 Project** κοινοποίησε μια δημοσίευση. ...
19 Σεπτεμβρίου · 🌐

Draxis
18 Σεπτεμβρίου · 🌐 👍 Μου αρέσει η Σελίδα!

Can we transform knowledge, Earth Observation & user-generated data into added value services for CAP monitoring? The answer is yes and it is called RECAP

Machi...
Δείτε περισσότερα

Δείτε τη μετάφραση

👤 Εσείς, Eirini Patsiali, Machi Simeonidou και 8 ακόμη

Ο χρήστης **RECAP H2020 Project** κοινοποίησε μια δημοσίευση. ...
19 Σεπτεμβρίου · 🌐

Draxis
18 Σεπτεμβρίου · 🌐 👍 Μου αρέσει η Σελίδα!

Can we transform knowledge, Earth Observation & user-generated data into added value services for CAP monitoring? The answer is yes and it is called RECAP

Machi...
Δείτε περισσότερα

Δείτε τη μετάφραση

👤 Εσείς, Eirini Patsiali, Machi Simeonidou και 8 ακόμη

Additionally the RECAP team sent out personal invitations to 171 stakeholders and representatives of major EU DGs Agencies, Paying Agencies, Academia, General Government, Agricultural Consultants etc.

The final workshop report “Insights of the RECAP project implementation” was also written and posted on RECAP webpage as well as partners’ presentations.

8.3 Insights of the final event

The workshop commenced with an introduction to the main challenges RECAP came to meet and the overall approach of the integrated system delivered transforming knowledge, Earth Observation & user-generated data into added value services for CAP monitoring.

Being the main integrated tool, the RECAP platform presentation followed, outlining the overall architecture, technologies and approaches used for the development of user driven (co-produced with end-users) personalized services supporting a better monitoring of the CAP for all the three main beneficiaries.

A focal point of the discussions was the Remote Sensing component of the RECAP platform and the results delivered within the testing and pilots implementation. Several interventions and questions from the audience focused on the technical aspects of the Remote Sensing tool and functionalities.

Pilot partners shared with the audience their experience in testing and validating the integrated RECAP platform and services, also transferring the experiences of farmers using the RECAP solutions as day-to-day tools.

*“Farmers using the RECAP platform have the opportunity to correct mistakes in their declarations – mistakenly declared crops types - avoiding any issues during the inspections”
Mr. Lafarga Alberto (INTIA) mentioned regarding the Spanish pilot case.*

9. Evaluation on the workshops results

Overall results are promising for RECAP's market uptake given that all user groups testing the platform in the workshops acknowledged it as an easy to use tool that can release them of significant administrative workload. Mainly it has been stated that RECAP tool is something they would consider using on an everyday basis.

Most of the farmers, identified as the most helpful functionality of the RECAP platform the receipt of simple advice tailored on each of the cross compliance and greening rules applying to every single plot they have declared. Such "personalized" information provided in an easy to understand way and simple language, helps farmers to save time and concentrate more in to their farming activity. This approach has been the foundation upon which the RECAP platform is developed, paving the way towards a guidance based system supporting farmers to understand CAP rules and comply with them, than penalizing them for non-compliance.

Agricultural consultants and advisors also identified this functionality as very helpful for farmers but also as a tool for direct communication and provision of e-advice to farmers. Using the Remote Sensing results advisors can inform farmers and correct any mistakenly declared plots, correct plot borders and any other mistakes which might cause potential non-compliance upon inspection.

When it comes to the final workshop, for the RECAP team, it was not an ending point. On the contrary it is seen as a starting point, for new initiatives for the delivery of user-driven solutions and added value services within the CAP monitoring.